

Construction and Field Evaluation of Electrically Isolated Tendons in a
Precast/Prestressed/Post-Tensioned Concrete Spliced Girder Bridge

Coplay Bridge (S.R. 704)

April 2020

By

Clay Naito, Ph.D., P.E.

ATLSS REPORT NO. 20-03

**ATLSS is a National Center for Engineering Research
on Advanced Technology for Large Structural Systems**

117 ATLSS Drive

Bethlehem, PA 18015-4729

Phone: (610)758-3525
Fax: (610)758-5902

www.atlss.lehigh.edu
Email: inatl@lehigh.edu

ABSTRACT

Electrically Isolated Tendon (EIT) systems appear to provide an effective means of ensuring the performance of post-tensioned strand systems. The systems are available commercially from more than one supplier and are marketed as being capable of assessing electrical isolation of a grouted duct from the completion of the grouting through the service life of the bridge. The system consists of specialty connections and isolation strategies, including plastic ducts and isolated anchorage blocks, among other components. Probes are connected to the strands which allow for the determination of the AC resistance between the strands internal to the duct and the reinforcement outside of the duct. The level of resistance is indicative of the level of isolation between the inside and outside of the post-tensioning ducts. A high degree of isolation would eliminate the possibility of an electrical cell to form and associated corrosion to initiate.

EIT systems have been used extensively in Europe but have not been executed in U.S. construction. A demonstration was conducted with support of the FHWA and Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. The system consists of a three-span continuous bridge composed of pretensioned Pennsylvania Bulb tees spliced and post-tensioned. The bridge system was monitored during beam fabrication, erection and bridge construction and an overview of the EIT installation methodology is presented. The performance of the EIT system is compared with standard recommendations on acceptable performance and was found to meet the requirements. Installation of the EIT system was not significantly different than that of a conventional post-tensioning tendon. The system provided additional assurance of the electrical isolation in the bridge and appears to be a viable approach for long term monitoring of the performance of post-tensioned grouted tendons. This report provides an overview on the project and outlines any hurdles that occurred during precast operations and erection.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Abstract.....	i
Table of Contents.....	ii
Table of Tables.....	iv
Table of Figures.....	v
1 Background on Electrically Isolated Tendons.....	1
1.1.1 Methodology.....	1
1.1.2 Limitations.....	5
1.1.3 Viability in Post-Tensioned Applications.....	6
2 Coplay Bridge Details.....	7
2.1 Plant Fabrication.....	7
2.2 Crack Formation.....	11
2.3 Field Construction.....	14
2.4 Coupling.....	14
2.5 Closure Pours and Pressure Check.....	17
2.6 Tensioning.....	18
2.7 Grouting.....	19
3 Overview of EIT Implementation in the Coplay Bridge.....	20
3.1 Post-Tensioned Bridge System Performance Concerns.....	20
3.2 EIT Tendon Systems.....	21
3.2.1 Recommended EIT Measurements.....	22
3.3 Coplay Bridge Demonstration.....	23
3.3.1 EIT System.....	24
3.3.2 Plant Fabrication.....	24
3.3.3 Field Construction.....	26
3.4 Monitoring and Performance.....	27
3.4.1 Acceptance Criteria.....	27
3.5 Recommendations.....	30
3.6 Discussion and Conclusions.....	31

4 EIT Measurement System.....32

4.1 EIT Monitoring System.....32

4.2 EIT Box Details34

4.3 LCR Meter Requirements37

4.4 Sample EIT Measurement Record38

5 Acknowledgements41

References42

Appendix A: Site Visit SummaryA

TABLE OF TABLES

Table 1: Sample cases of post-tension tendon corrosion	20
Table 2: Specific resistance measurements for Coplay Bridge.....	28
Table 3: EIT Box Hardware	35

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Electrically isolated tendon schematic (Figure adapted from (D. Vedova and Elsener 2006))	2
Figure 2: Connection box for impedance measurements (Bernhard Elsener 2004)	2
Figure 3: Principle of measuring the electrical impedance of a tendon with the LCR meter (Bernhard Elsener and Büchler 2011)	3
Figure 4: Electrical equivalent circuit for an electrically isolated tendon with small defect (Bernhard Elsener and Büchler 2011)	3
Figure 5: Limit Values (28 days after injection)	4
Figure 6: Evolution of electrical resistance over time (D. Vedova and Elsener 2006)	5
Figure 7: Coplay Bridge Layout	7
Figure 8: Grout connections in duct	7
Figure 9: Layout of PT ducts	8
Figure 10: Duct protection at stirrups	8
Figure 11: Isolated anchorage head	9
Figure 12: Non-isolated anchorage head	9
Figure 13: End anchorages	9
Figure 14: Reinforcement installation	10
Figure 15: Grout vent detail	11
Figure 16: Grout vents in ducts	11
Figure 17: Hairline cracks near top PT ducts	12
Figure 18: Beam S5-A1 Cracks	12
Figure 19: Beam S5-B1 Cracks	12
Figure 20: Beam S5-C1 Cracks	13
Figure 21: Beam S5-D1 Cracks	13
Figure 22: Beam S5-E1 Cracks	13
Figure 23: Piers prior to beam erection	14
Figure 24: Erection of span 6 beams	14
Figure 25: Typical coupling details	15
Figure 26: Duct coupling	15
Figure 27: Closure pour diaphragm 1 after coupling	16
Figure 28: Alternate coupling detail at closure pour diaphragm	16
Figure 29: Lap splicing at closure pours	17
Figure 30: Plan view of closure pour	17
Figure 31: Section view of closure pour	18
Figure 32: Elevation view of closure pour	18
Figure 33: Stressing sequence	19
Figure 34: EIT circuit	22

Figure 35: Monitoring of EIT system	23
Figure 36: Coplay bridge configuration.....	24
Figure 37: Standard and EIT post-tensioning trumpet details	25
Figure 38: Duct details	25
Figure 39: Field construction details	27
Figure 40: Specific resistance measurements of EIT system.....	29
Figure 41: Specific capacitance measurements of EIT system.....	30
Figure 42: Loss factor measurements of EIT system.....	30
Figure 43: EIT junction box location.....	32
Figure 44: EIT and strand wire housing in diaphragm	33
Figure 45: Conduit connection to strands	33
Figure 46: EIT box close-up	34
Figure 47: Wiring diagram for EIT Box	35
Figure 48: BK LCR Meter Specification Sheet	38
Figure 49: Coplay recorded raw data.....	39
Figure 50: Sample blank data sheet	40

1 BACKGROUND ON ELECTRICALLY ISOLATED TENDONS

Electrically isolated tendons (EIT) are an enhanced tendon/anchorage detailing system used in bonded post-tensioned systems. One of the main advantages in comparison to traditional tendon/anchorage systems is that an EIT system provides enhanced corrosion protection of the tendons and allows for quality control during construction and monitoring during the service life of the system (D. Vedova and Elsener 2006). EIT systems are typically used in situations where corrosion due to stray current is a potential issue or in systems where a high level of protection of the strands is desired. In addition to quality control monitoring, the EIT system also has the potential to identify breaches in the corrosion protection system of the tendon throughout the service life of the structure by monitoring for the ingress of water into the grouted duct.

1.1.1 Methodology

The electrically isolated tendon system for internal grouted post-tensioning applications was developed to provide an increased level of protection and provide monitoring capability of the tendons. Electrically isolated tendons differ from typical post-tensioned system details in that they provide full electrical isolation of the PT tendons from the normal rebar network. This requires the use of electrically isolated anchor heads, corrugated plastic ducts (polyethylene or polypropylene), and special care at grout vents. Detailing of EITs is critical to the effective implementation of the system, particularly near the anchorages in order to ensure complete encapsulation and electrical isolation. An overview of the design of an electrically isolated system is provided by (D. Vedova and Elsener 2006). The following provides a summary of the detailing required at the anchorage region to ensure electrical isolation of the system.

In order to achieve electrical isolation a mechanically resistant insulation plate is placed between the steel anchor head with wedges that block the strand and cast-iron bearing plate. This electrically isolates the tendon from the non-prestressed reinforcement network. In addition, a plastic trumpet is tightly connected to the duct inside the anchorage to isolate the strand from the cast-iron bearing anchorage. An electric terminal must be attached to the anchorage head and appropriately routed to allow access for impedance measurements. It is important that an access box be used to collect the electrical terminals from the tendons and that it be positioned to provide easy access for future inspection and maintenance personnel (D. Vedova and Elsener 2006). A schematic of a typical electrically isolated tendon anchorage is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Electrically isolated tendon schematic (Figure adapted from (D. Vedova and Elsener 2006))

One of the major advantages of using electrically isolated tendons is that the corrosion protection of the steel strands can be monitored during construction and throughout the service life of the structure using AC impedance measurements (electrical resistance measurements). The impedance measurements require a sound electrical connection to each tendon and an additional connection to the non-prestressed reinforcement in the component (Bernhard Elsener 2004). Typically, all connection wires are routed to an accessible connection box, which will be used by inspectors to take measurements (Figure 2). The impedance measurements are taken with a portable LCR meter, which can measure the inductance (L), the capacitance (C), and resistance (R) of a component. For the chosen measurement frequency the LCR meter then calculates and displays the ohmic resistance (R), the capacitance (C), and the loss factor (D), which are then recorded by the inspector (Bernhard Elsener 2004).

Figure 2: Connection box for impedance measurements (Bernhard Elsener 2004)

The impedance measurements taken are performed between the steels stand in the duct and the normal (non-prestressed) reinforcement network in the concrete (Figure 3). Therefore, the measuring system includes the grout within the duct, the duct itself (including any defects) and the concrete surrounding the duct (Elsener and Buchler, 2011). The concrete and grout are pure resistances (in the range of measuring frequencies between 100 and 1000 Hz),

in contrast the plastic duct is in essence a capacitance in parallel with a very high resistance (Figure 4), as a result system defects and/or imperfections are represented by ohmic resistance in parallel (Bernhard Elsener 2008). The ohmic resistance, capacitance, and loss factor measurements can determine the degree of electrical isolation at any time after grouting, which is used for quality control and long term monitoring of the corrosion protection of the tendons (D. Vedova and Elsener 2006).

Figure 3: Principle of measuring the electrical impedance of a tendon with the LCR meter (Bernhard Elsener and Büchler 2011)

Figure 4: Electrical equivalent circuit for an electrically isolated tendon with small defect (Bernhard Elsener and Büchler 2011)

It is recommended by (Bernhard Elsener and Büchler 2011) that impedance measurements be taken after the tendons have been stressed but before introducing the grouting material. These resistance measurements can be used to identify short circuits or unexpected low impedance values between the prestressing strands and the normal reinforcement, allowing the possibility for repairs to be made. For quality control purposes in order for electrically isolated tendons to meet the acceptance criteria resistance measurements must be taken after the tendon is grouted and compared to the published limiting values (Figure 5). Based on the 2007 revision to the Swiss guideline “Measures to Ensure Durability of Post-Tensioning Tendons in Structures,” the electrical resistance measurements may be performed

anytime between 7 and 56 days and normalizing the measured values to 28 days. In addition, the acceptance criteria have been adjusted to reflect the various applications for which EIT can be specified; preventing fretting between the normal reinforcement and prestressing strand (fatigue), use for the purpose of long-term monitoring (monitoring) and for protection against stray current (stray current).

Main Criteria	Monitoring Minimum value of the length normalised electrical resistance ⁵⁾ $R_l (=R \cdot L_p)$	Fatigue Minimum value of the electrical resistance R	Stray Current ⁶⁾ Minimum value of the length normalised electrical resistance ⁵⁾ $R_l (=R \cdot L_p)$
Duct			
ϕ 60 mm	50 k Ω m	20 Ω	250 k Ω m
ϕ 75 mm	50 k Ω m	20 Ω	200 k Ω m
ϕ 100 mm	50 k Ω m	20 Ω	150 k Ω m
ϕ 130 mm	50 k Ω m	20 Ω	125 k Ω m
Maximum allowed failure rate	10%	0 ⁷⁾	20%

Figure 5: Limit Values (28 days after injection)

For long term monitoring the resistance values can be analyzed over time to provide information on the condition of the corrosion protection system. A continuous increase in the resistance measurements over time is expected due to the hydration of the grout and concrete surrounding the tendon. Figure 6 shows an example of the increasing trend of electrical resistance measurements that is expected with time. Based on this principle that the resistance measurements should increase over time early warning signs of a breach in the corrosion protection system can potentially be identified by deviations from the trend line (decreasing resistance measurements). It should be noted that it is important to monitor the temperature at the time of inspection because temperature variations can cause some variation in the expected measurements.

As previously mentioned, a deviation in the trend of the resistance measurements over time can indicate that a defect in the corrosion protection system is present. An increase in moisture level of the grout or concrete is typically the cause of the decrease in measured resistance, so the ingress of water potentially containing chlorides can be identified at an early stage. If inspections are conducted at regular intervals the electrical impedance measurements can provide early warnings that the corrosion protection system has been breached before corrosion begins (B. Elsener 2005).

Figure 6: Evolution of electrical resistance over time (D. Vedova and Elsener 2006)

The use of electrically isolated tendons for monitoring purposes have been tested in laboratory experiments (Bernhard Elsener 2004; 2008; Bernhard Elsener and Büchler 2011) and have more recently been implemented in a number of post-tensioned bridges in Switzerland and Italy (D. Vedova and Elsener 2006; M. D. Vedova, Elsener, and Evangelista 2004) where data measurements for quality control monitoring have been collected and published. In addition, guidelines for implementing electrically isolated tendons into post-tensioned construction have been developed and published in a Swiss guideline “Measures to Ensure Durability of Post-Tensioning Tendons in Structures” (ASTRA, 2007). Example of bridges where electrically isolated tendons are current implemented include Piacenza Viaduct and Marchiazza Viaduct in Italy and P.S. du Milieu, Wiesebrucke Basel and Glattal Viaduct in Switzerland.

1.1.2 Limitations

One of the limitations that arise with respect to NDE using electrically isolated tendons is that fact that this type of evaluation cannot be used on existing systems with conventional non-isolated tendon/anchorage detailing. When implementing EITs into new construction extreme care must be taken during the construction phase to ensure that electrical isolation of the tendon is achieved. If a short circuit is present then future NDE is not possible, making the system ineffective. Currently the acceptance criteria for EITs is strict but can be achieved if there is adequate planning and detailing in the design stage assuring there is room for the tendon between normal rebar, careful workmanship during the construction phase and the control over the ducts for leaks at joints, couplers, welding or defects is taken (B. Elsener 2005).

Another limitation of the EIT system is that it although it can potentially identify breeches in the corrosion protection system the method cannot currently identify the location of defect along length of the tendon. Being able to determine the location of the damage along the length tendon would be an area worth investigating for improvement of the EIT system. The information gained by being able to determine defect location would make this a more complete system

by allowing the area of damage to quickly be investigated with respect to durability and allow for repairs to be made. Some recent efforts have been made to determine if applying the magnetic flux method using the electrical connections between the prestressing strand and normal reinforcing can be used to successfully identify defect location along the strand (Bernhard Elsener and Büchler 2011). It should also be noted that although these systems have been implemented there have been no known cases where damage has been identified based on long term monitoring techniques. This may be attributed to the fact that these systems have not been in place long enough (15-20 years) where corrosion of the tendons is expected, but this should continue to be investigated over time to establish the capability for long term monitoring.

1.1.3 Viability in Post-Tensioned Applications

Electrically isolated tendons are applicable where internal grouted tendons require the highest level of protection and/or for monitoring of the tendons for quality control and throughout the life of the structure. Currently the main advantage of this system is the ability to provide quality control measurements leading to an overall higher level of protection for the strands. The condition of the corrosion protection system, particularly the ability to the ingress of water can potentially be detected through long term monitoring of the impedance measurements. This method can be used to identify early warning signs of deterioration to the corrosion protection system identifying possible tendon corrosion. NDE using EITs cannot be applied to as built systems that do not already have electrically isolated tendons. NDE of the EITs using impedance measurements appears to be viable tool to monitor the corrosion protection system of the tendon based on the presented literature. It is recommended that the EIT system be examined further to verify its ability to detect breaches in the corrosion protection system as well as potential to identify location of defects along the length of the tendon.

2 COPLAY BRIDGE DETAILS

The EIT system will be integrated into a precast / prestressed / post-tensioned spliced girder bridge. The bridge is part of a replacement project conducted by Pennsylvania Department of Transportation (PennDOT). The bridge is located in Northampton and Lehigh Counties State Route 7404 Section 07M. The bridge is located in the borough of Coplay and is herein referred to as the Coplay Bridge (pronounced cop – lay). The bridge consists of eight spans bridging over Bridge Street, the Ironton Rail Trail, the Lehigh River, and the Norfolk Southern Rail Road Line (Figure 7).

The bridge consists of three approach spans to the west of the river (Spans 1, 2 and 3) and two approach spans to the east of the river (Spans 7 and 8). A spliced post-tensioned girder system is utilized for the main spans of the bridge (Span 4, 5 and 6). Five spliced prestressed / post-tensioned concrete PA bulb tees are used across the 44 ft wide deck.

Figure 7: Coplay Bridge Layout

2.1 Plant Fabrication

The precast/prestressed concrete beams were fabricated at the Northeast Prestressed Products plant in Cressona, PA. Figure 7 below shows a corrugated PP duct before and after one of the grout connections was installed.

Figure 8: Grout connections in duct

The post-tensioning ducts were laid out in the plant as shown below in Figure 8. At locations where the duct is resting on stirrups, a duct protection was provided (Figure 9). The top duct in Figure 8 is the EIT duct, and the yellow heat shrink sleeves signify the location of a splice.

Figure 9: Layout of PT ducts

Figure 10: Duct protection at stirrups

At the ends of the beam, anchorages were fabricated for the EIT duct and the non-isolated ducts. The isolated and non-isolated anchorage heads for the ducts are shown in Figures 10 and 11, respectively. Figure 12 shows the end anchorages for the ducts, the black anchorage being for the EIT duct.

Figure 11: Isolated anchorage head

Figure 12: Non-isolated anchorage head

Figure 13: End anchorages

The steel reinforcement was installed in the plant, as illustrated below in Figure 13. Grout vents were also installed along each of the ducts per the detail in Figure 14. Figure 15 shows the installed vents on the ducts.

Figure 14: Reinforcement installation

Figure 15: Grout vent detail

Figure 16: Grout vents in ducts

2.2 Crack Formation

After the beams were fabricated in the plant, hairline cracks were observed near the top of each beam, as shown below in Figure 17. It was noted that the cracks on each of the beams appear to line up closely to the location of the top PT ducts, which are the electrically isolated ducts. Figure 18 to Figure 22 below illustrate the location of the cracks (shown in red) in relation to the tendons for beams (shown in blue) S5-A1 through S5-E1. These figures show how closely the cracks follow the path of the top ducts in each beam. For each beam, the average crack width was measured to be about 0.002-0.003 inches.

Figure 17: Hairline cracks near top PT ducts

Figure 18: Beam S5-A1 Cracks

Figure 19: Beam S5-B1 Cracks

Figure 20: Beam S5-C1 Cracks

Figure 21: Beam S5-D1 Cracks

Figure 22: Beam S5-E1 Cracks

According to AASHTO LRFD 8th Edition Section 5.4.6.2, “the size of ducts in cast-in-place concrete shall not exceed 0.4 times the least gross concrete thickness at the duct” (AASHTO 2017). In the Copley Bridge, the ducts have a diameter of 3.375 inches, and the least gross concrete thickness is the web of the beams, which is 8.5 inches. For an 8.5-in. wide web, the ducts must not exceed 3.4 inches, so the ducts in this case meet that requirement. However, with the addition of the duct half shell support, the outer diameter ends up being 5.32 inches, which exceeds the AASHTO requirement at the duct support locations. Section 5.4.6.2 of AASHTO also requires that “the duct area shall be at least 2.5 times the net area of the prestressing steel” when tendons are placed by the pull-through method (AASHTO 2017). With 15 – 0.6 in. diameter strands in each tendon, the duct area must be at least 8.14 in². The ducts used in these beams have a total cross-sectional area of 8.95 in², therefore satisfying the AASHTO requirement. The majority of past EIT installations appear to be in cast-in-place post-tensioned systems or larger box beams. For these systems the webs tend to be much more substantial. It is recommended that this issue be examined in the future to minimize the potential for reflective cracking in the precast beam webs.

2.3 Field Construction

After fabricating the beams in the plant, the beams were delivered to the site to be erected. The five haunch beams on the Northampton side of construction were erected first, followed by the splice beams for span 6 (between piers 5 and 6). The same sequence is followed on the Copley side of construction, with the span 5 drop in beams to be placed last. Figure 23 shows a view of the piers from the Copley side of construction before placing the beams. The erection of the span 6 beams is shown in Figure 24.

Figure 23: Piers prior to beam erection

Figure 24: Erection of span 6 beams

2.4 Coupling

The corrugated PP ducts surrounding the post-tensioning strands require coupling where two ends of the ducts meet. The ducts are coupled using either an HDPE slip-on coupler or a polyethylene stepless duct coupler. Typical coupling details are shown below in Figure 25. As illustrated in the figure, at duct to duct connections not located at a closure

pour diaphragm, a 3-3/8 in. slip-on coupler is used. At each of the closure pour diaphragms, a 3-3/8 in. stepless duct coupler is used. Figure 26 shows an example of the coupled ducts prior to applying the heat shrink sleeves. Closure pour diaphragm 1 after the ducts have been coupled is shown in Figure 27.

Figure 25: Typical coupling details

Figure 26: Duct coupling

Figure 27: Closure pour diaphragm 1 after coupling

At the closure pours, most duct projections at the beam ends were 6 in. which is consistent with the contract drawings. However, at a few locations, the duct projections were trimmed to about 4 in. to decrease the potential for duct damage during the beam erection process. At these locations where the ducts project 4 in., an alternate coupling detail was specified, as shown below in Figure 28. This alternate detail specifies a 3-3/8 in. polyethylene stepless duct coupler at the closure pours, a 3-3/4 in. long PP duct is now needed in the gap between the trimmed duct ends.

**DUCT TO DUCT CONNECTION AT CLOSURE POUR
ALTERNATE DETAIL**

Figure 28: Alternate coupling detail at closure pour diaphragm

2.5 Closure Pours and Pressure Check

Within spans 4, 5, and 6 of Coplay Bridge, there are a total of four closure pour diaphragms in which there is a 12 in. splice. After the precast beam segments have been erected, each of the ducts at the closure pours must be coupled as discussed above. Prior to casting the closure pours, the protruding prestress strands should be lap spliced as shown below in Figure 29. The prestress strands extend 10 in. from the face of each precast girder, and where they overlap 8 in., they must be lap spliced using tie wire.

Figure 29: Lap splicing at closure pours

After lap splicing the prestress strands, the closure pours can be cast, and the concrete can gain the required strength. Figure 30, Figure 31, and Figure 32, respectively, show a plan, section, and elevation view of a typical closure pour. Once the concrete in the closure pours has gained the required strength, the post-tensioning strands can be installed through the ducts.

Figure 30: Plan view of closure pour

Figure 31: Section view of closure pour

Figure 32: Elevation view of closure pour

After casting the closure pours, a pressure test is conducted to ensure that the fully assembled system is sufficiently leak tight. This system test follows the requirements of FIB Technical Report, Bulletin 7, titled “Corrugated Plastic Ducts for Internal Bonded Post-Tensioning.” The duct is subjected to a constant air pressure of 0.1 bar from the inside. Over a period of five minutes, the loss of air/leakage rate should be measured with a flowmeter and the values recorded. If the pressure loss over the period of five minutes does not exceed 10% of the initial pressure, the leak tightness is deemed acceptable.

2.6 Tensioning

Once the closure pours have been completed, the isolation plates, PE spacers, and wedge plates are installed, and stressing can proceed. The tendons are stressed from both ends one at a time once the concrete in all the closure pours

has reached its minimum required strength. Figure 33 below shows the stressing sequence in the five beams across the bridge.

Figure 33: Stressing sequence

As this figure illustrates, tendons T3 are all stressed followed by tendons T2, T1 (EIT tendons), and lastly, T4. Stressing begins in the center beam, B18, then moves to B19 and B17 before doing the outside beams, B16 and B20. After all the tendons have been stressed and the engineer’s approval is obtained, the strand tails should be cut by an abrasive saw.

2.7 Grouting

The grouting operation has a large impact on the durability of the post-tensioned system, so it is essential that it is done correctly. For this project, Five Star High Performance Precision Non-Shrink Grout was used. Prior to grouting, it is important to check the installation and position of any vents and drains. The typical procedure for grouting includes starting at one tendon end until grout is seen flowing out of the first vent. This vent is then closed, and grouting continues in a similar manner until grout of correct consistency flows out of the last vent. This vent is closed, and pressure is maintained for about a minute before closing the inlet.

3 OVERVIEW OF EIT IMPLEMENTATION IN THE COPLAY BRIDGE

A journal publication was developed that summarizes the EIT installation and performance on the Coplay Bridge. This paper has been published in ASCE Journal of Bridge Engineering (Naito 2020). The information contained in the manuscript is reproduced in this chapter.

Naito, C., "Construction and Field Evaluation of Electrically Isolated Tendons in a Prestressed Concrete Spliced Girder Bridge," Case Study, ASCE Bridge Journal, Vol. 25, No. 7, July 2020, Submitted April 2019, Accepted Dec. 2019, [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)BE.1943-5592.0001551](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)BE.1943-5592.0001551).

3.1 Post-Tensioned Bridge System Performance Concerns

Post-tensioning (PT) systems have been successfully used for moderate span bridge construction since the 1950s and continues to be an effective method of construction for major U.S. construction projects such as the San Francisco Oakland Bay Bridge East Span completed in 2013. One of the principal issues regarding the use of grouted post-tensioned duct systems is the inability to readily inspect the grout placement within the ducts and the condition of the tendons during construction and service. Issues that can arise include: (1) voids due to insufficient grouting which can result in water accumulation from initial bleed or through intrusion; (2) physical grout deficiencies such as the inability to set, segregate, or the formation of soft regions; (3) elevated chloride content of the grout due to errors in manufacturing of the prepackaged mix (Hartt and Lee 2018); (4) infiltration of chloride laden water during service due to poor detailing; (5) unexpected cracking in plastic ducts (Suarez et al. 2006). All of these issues can result in corrosion initiation in the tendons and if left unchecked can result in significant damage and the potential for closure of the bridge. Such damage has been observed sporadically for post-tensioned bridge systems over the past 50 years, as noted in Table 1. The degree of damage observed varied and included significant tendon corrosion, complete failure of tendons, and in some extreme cases, complete collapse of the bridge. Note that no known collapses of post-tensioned systems have occurred in the U.S. due to the biennial safety inspections conducted as part of federally mandated standards of care. In addition, issues such as the elevated grout chlorides have been addressed and mitigated in U.S. construction. Nevertheless, in many cases, even those where the tendons did not reach the point of failure, the corrosion observed was significant enough to result in bridge closure and significant repairs to the system.

Bridge Name	Bridge Type	Location	Year	Observed Damage	Causes of Corrosion
Bickton Meadows Footbridge	Precast Segmental	UK	1967	Bridge Collapse	Mortar joints allowed moisture, chlorides and oxygen transport at joints (Trejo et al. 2009)
Ynys-Y-Gwas (Woodward 1981)	Segmental PT	Whales	1985	Bridge Collapse	Transverse joints between segments filled with dry mortar caulking allowing water infiltration (Trejo et al. 2009)
Malle Bridge (Mathy et al. 1996)	Precast Segmental	Belgium	1992	Bridge Collapse	Voids in duct and ingress of water and chlorides
Niles Channel Bridge (Powers, Sagiúés, and Virmani, n.d.)	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder	Florida	1999	Tendon Failure	Water infiltration into tendon anchorage with voids

Table 1: Sample cases of post-tension tendon corrosion

Mid Bay Bridge (Corven Engineering, Inc. 2001)	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder	Florida	2000	Tendon Failure	Cracked post tensioning ducts and exposed strand along water bleed trails
Sunshine Skyway	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder / Cable Stay	Florida	2000	Tendon Failure	Poor grout quality/practices, voids near anchorage, cracked polyethylene ducts, water infiltration through segmental joints(Trejo et al. 2009)
Varina-Enon Bridge	Cable Stay with PT Box Girder	Virginia	2001	Tendon Failure	Voids in tendons and absence of grout (Trejo et al. 2009)
Plymouth Ave Bridge (Berg and Schokker 2012)	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder	Minnesota	2010	Tendon Failure	Leak in drainage system internal to box and corrosion of lower box tendon
Ringling Causeway(Goldsberry 2013)	Precast Segmental PT Box Girder	Florida	2011	Tendon Failure	Deficient Grout (Grout having high moisture content, high pore water pH, low total chloride concentrations and high sulfate concentrations)

While strict quality control methods can be implemented to improve performance of materials and non-destructive evaluation methods can be employed during construction, unexpected problems with the PT system such as accidental leakage at joints or poor drainage cannot be easily detected. Electrically isolated tendon (EIT) systems can be implemented to address these concerns. This paper provides an overview of an EIT system and a case study of its implementation and performance in a Pennsylvania bridge.

3.2 EIT Tendon Systems

EIT has been developed for internal grouted post-tensioning applications to provide an increased level of corrosion protection and to provide monitoring capability of the tendons during construction and service. A sufficient level of isolation for a typical bridge service life can be achieved with the use of corrugated plastic ducts (polyethylene or polypropylene) combined with traditional post-tension anchorage and splice hardware. A highest level of corrosion protection can be achieved with a complete EIT system which can provide full electrical isolation of the PT tendons within the duct from reinforcement in the beam. This requires the use of electrically isolated anchor heads, plastic ducts, and special care at grout vents and splices. Detailing of EITs is critical to the effective implementation of the system, particularly near the anchorages in order to ensure complete encapsulation and electrical isolation. While initial implementation of plastic ducts occurred in the 1960’s a concerted effort to develop a full EIT system did not take place until the 1985 construction of the Zurich railway station which required special protection against the stray currents at the station (Bernhard Elsener 2004). The EIT concept has been examined in depth by Elsener and others (Bernhard Elsener 2004; D. Vedova and Elsener 2006). EIT systems have been used in various post-tensioned concrete bridges in Europe, including the Piacenza Viaduct and Marchiazza Viaduct in Italy and the P.S. du Milieu and the Wiesebrücke Basel in Switzerland. Guidelines are available on the use of the system from the Swiss (Bernhard Elsener and Büchler 2011), the International Federation for Structural Concrete fib 33 (Fuzier, Ganz, and Matt 2005), and a draft guideline is under development for U.S. applications (Angst and Buchler 2015). The Post-Tensioning Institute and the American Segmental Bridge Institute also outlines approaches that can be followed to achieve various levels of protection (Post-Tensioning Institute (PTI) and American Segmental Bridge Institute (ASBI) 2012).

The goal of the EIT system is to provide complete encapsulation of the tendon from the material exterior to the tendon. The system can be represented as a circuit as illustrated in Figure 34. The AC impedance is measured between the encapsulated tendon and the reinforcement within the concrete member. As part of the circuit, the grout acts as a resistor, the tendon/duct/reinforcement a capacitor, and the concrete a resistor. The presence of any defects along the length of the duct will act in parallel to the capacitor resulting in a significant decrease in the impedance between the tendon and the reinforcing steel.

Figure 34: EIT circuit

3.2.1 Recommended EIT Measurements

The AC impedance measurements for the EIT system consists of the resistance, capacitance and loss factor (Angst and Buchler 2015). The resistance, R , is the measurement of the resistance between the encapsulated tendon and the steel reinforcement in the surrounding concrete. High values of resistance are indicative of a high level of encapsulation. Large breaches in the system combined with moisture will result in very low resistance between the tendon within the duct and the reinforcement outside the duct. Consequently, the magnitude of the resistance and changes in the resistance over time can be used as an indicator of the effectiveness and temporal changes in the encapsulation. The post-tensioning system also acts as a capacitor, with the tendon acting as one conductive material, the conventional reinforcement acting as the other, and the polyethylene duct acting as a dielectric between the two conductors. A change in the capacitance is indicative of a change in the permittivity (i.e., a change in the dielectric properties) due to changes in the integrity of the duct. A real capacitor will have some resistive current running between conductive materials and can be modeled as an equivalent series resistor (ESR) in series with an ideal capacitor. The loss factor, also commonly referred to as the dissipation factor, provides a measure of the dielectric material's ability to absorb energy when an AC signal is applied. The loss factor is the ratio of the real and imaginary components of the impedance (Angst and Buchler 2015). Increases in the loss factor are indicative of higher energy dissipation in the real capacitor which is indicative of problems with the encapsulation.

Measurements are typically taken at one end of the bridge but provide an assessment of the integrity of the entire tendon length, L . Since the tendon and reinforcement have negligible resistance, the presence of defects in the tendon encapsulation at any point along the duct length will result in a decrease in resistance or increase in capacitance and

loss factor. The resistance and capacitance are normalized by the tendon length resulting in the specific resistance, R_i , and specific capacitance, C_i , for the system as noted in Equation 1 and 2.

$$R_i = R \cdot L \quad [\Omega \cdot m] \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

$$C_i = C/L \quad [F/m] \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

The loss factor, D , is a unitless term which is independent of the length of the duct and increases in magnitude with the number of defects.

The standard measurements taken for an EIT system include the resistance, capacitance, and loss factor. It is important to note that the measurements are sensitive to the excitation voltage, measuring frequency and the temperature of the system. The details of the bridge including the length of the EIT tendon, the date and time of the reading, and the temperature should be noted. The impedance measurements can be taken with a portable Inductance/Capacitance/Resistance (LCR) meter as noted schematically in Figure 34 and shown in Figure 35. As noted in fib bulletin 33 (Fuzier, Ganz, and Matt 2005, 33), the measurements should be taken with the LCR meter set in parallel to the EIT circuit with a measuring frequency of 1 kHz and a minimum AC excitation voltage of 0.5 V.

Figure 35: Monitoring of EIT system

3.3 Copley Bridge Demonstration

A demonstration project was implemented by the Federal Highway Administration and Pennsylvania Department of Transportation in collaboration with Northampton and Lehigh County to assess the viability, ease of use, and operation of the EIT system. The bridge system consists of precast/prestressed Pennsylvania bulb tee girders spliced and post-tensioned in place. The bridge is part of a replacement project conducted by Pennsylvania Department of Transportation (PennDOT) on behalf of Lehigh County. The bridge crosses from Lehigh to Northampton County on State Route 7404. The bridge is located in the borough of Copley and is herein referred to as the Copley Bridge (pronounced kăp lă). The bridge consists of eight spans bridging over Bridge Street, the Ironton Rail Trail, the Lehigh River, and the Norfolk Southern Rail Road Line. The bridge consists of three approach spans to the west of the river (Spans 1, 2 and 3) and two approach spans to the east of the river (Spans 7 and 8). A spliced post-tensioned girder system is utilized for the main spans of the bridge (Span 4, 5 and 6). Five spliced prestressed / post-tensioned concrete PA bulb tees spaced at approximately 3.12m (10'-3") are used across the 13.62 m (44' - 8 1/4") wide deck.

Figure 36: Copley bridge configuration

3.3.1 EIT System

The project was competitively bid and the contractor selected Dywidag Systems International (DSI) to provide the post-tensioning system. Each of the five beam lines contained four post-tensioning ducts with each duct containing fifteen 0.6 in. (15 mm) diameter grade 270 low relaxation strands conforming to ASTM A416 (ASTM International 2017, 416). To compare conventional and EIT construction details both systems were integrated into each beam. The top tendon line in each beam was designed with full isolation, the bottom three were designed with standard hardware. The fabrication was conducted in two phases: plant fabrication and field operations. The pretensioned beams were precast at Northeast Prestressed Products in Cressona, PA. The field operations included the delivery, via truck 72.4 km (45 miles), erection onsite by Structural Services, beam splicing, placement of closure joints, post-tension application, and the diaphragms and deck placement by Trumbull Corporation. Details of these two phases with respect to the EIT system are outlined in the following sections.

3.3.2 Plant Fabrication

Both tendon systems include an anchorage head, trumpet, duct, and couplers. The duct system in both cases are comprised of 85 mm (3.35 in.) internal diameter corrugated polypropylene ducts with O.D. of 100.2 mm (3.95 in.) and wall thickness of 2.54 mm (0.10 in.) conforming to ASTM D4101 (ASTM Standard D4101-17 2017). To provide isolation of the tendon all strands are encapsulated through special detailing from one anchor head to the other. The anchor head is covered with a plastic grout cap and the grout tube is sealed with a polyethylene cap after the grout has hardened. The strand wedges and wedge plate are steel but they bear on a non-conductive electrical isolation plate attached to the metal anchor body. A plastic trumpet is used within the anchor body and includes a lip which is sandwiched between the isolation plate and anchor body thus preventing electrical continuity of the tendon grout (Figure 37). Ducts are coupled with a polypropylene slip-on coupler and sealed with heat shrink sleeves field cut to 111 mm (4 3/8 in.). Grout vents and drains are fabricated by drilling holes in the duct and creating a weld with the polyethylene port connection. To minimize potential damage to the ducts during fabrication and stressing protective half-shells are used where the duct is supported by transverse reinforcement and secured using plastic zip ties (Figure 38). Following precast operations the ducts were inspected to ensure that no obstructions were present in the duct. A steel cylinder, sized to match the area of strands expected, was run through each duct and no conflicts were found. The ducts were then capped at each end to prevent any debris or moisture from entering the ducts during storage and

transportation. The precast producer found no tangible difference in the installation labor between the EIT and non-EIT anchorage heads, trumpets, ducts and couplers.

Figure 37: Standard and EIT post-tensioning trumpet details

Figure 38: Duct details

3.3.3 *Field Construction*

The beams were erected on the completed piers and two temporary shoring towers as noted in Figure 36 and shown in Figure 39. Strongbacks were used to provide temporary bracing and to assist with alignment at each closure joint (Figure 39). The ducts were spliced at each closure joint in the field using a polypropylene coupler sealed with heat shrink sleeves field cut to 111 mm (4 3/8 in.). The required splice distance between beams at the closure joint location was designated as 305 mm (12 in.). This limited space required any coupling materials to be placed over the extended ducts prior to erection. To properly measure the level of electrical isolation in the tendon along the bridge length, the electrical continuity of the conventional reinforcement in each spliced beam needed to be maintained. As illustrated in Figure 38, pretensioning strands were used in each beam segment to ensure continuity. These bare strands were tied to the transverse reinforcement cage within each beam during plant fabrication, thus providing steel-to-steel contact within the body of each beam. At the end of each precast beam segment two of the pretensioning strands were left extending 25.4 cm (10 in.) from each face. These strands were overlapped 203 mm (8 in.) and fastened together at each closure joint ensure electrical continuity of all the reinforcement along the length of the bridge. Note that two strands were used to provide redundancy. Details of the field connections are illustrated in Figure 39.

Once the closure pours were completed, the strands were run through the ducts, the isolation plates and wedge plates were installed, and stressing was conducted. The tendons were stressed from both ends one at a time once the concrete in all the closure pours had reached the minimum required strength. After stressing, the duct was pressurized to 138 kPa (20 psi) internal pressure with oil and water-free compressed air. The pressure integrity was checked by locking off the outside air source for 1 minute. The test was required in the design specification and was intended to check for leaks in the duct system prior to grout placement and was not intended to be an air-tightness test of the system. During the pre-grouting air pressure test, beam D exhibited a marginal loss of pressure. The leak was identified as cross-communication between the adjacent ducts. While the exact location could not be identified it is likely that a pathway may have formed through the heat shrink splice at one of the closure joints. The remaining ducts were able to hold pressure without incident.

The ducts were grouted within 7 days of stressing. The grout was required to meet a number of performance requirements including: chloride permeability of less than 2500 coulombs tested in accordance with ASTM C1202 (ASTM Standard C1202-19 2019), chloride ion content less than 0.08% by weight of cementitious material, set time between 3 and 12 hours tested in accordance with ASTM C953 (ASTM Standard C953-17 2017), and grout strength greater than 20.7 MPa (3 ksi) at 7 days and 34.5 MPa (5 ksi) at 28 days tested in accordance with ASTM C942 (ASTM Standard C942-15 2015). A special inspection of all anchorage outlets and high point outlets was performed after 24 hours to identify the presence of soft grout. The grout mix consisted of 22.7 kg (50 lbs) of Euclid PTX with 5.7 to 6.4 liters (1.5 to 1.7 gal) of potable water. Pretesting of the grout met all requirements. The grout was tested with both water levels and resulted in a set time of 9.5 to 11 hours, 0.011% chloride by weight of mixed grout, rapid chloride permeability ranging from 306 to 388 coulombs at 28 days, compressive strength of 49 to 58 MPa (7110 to 8470 psi) at 7 days and 68 to 75 MPa (9880 to 10900 psi) at 28 days. Soft grout was not observed on the bridge.

Figure 39: Field construction details

To facilitate intermittent monitoring of the EIT system a junction box was installed on the pier of the bridge. The measurements were taken at pier 3. As previously mentioned, the top tendon in each beam was fully encapsulated and the remaining three were conventionally constructed. One lead wire (AWG #12 Copper wire double sheathed) was attached to the wedge plate with a hex head screw. This connection was encapsulated in grout within the plastic anchorage grout cap as illustrated in Figure 39. These connections are denoted AE through EE, for beams A through E in Figure 35. Two additional connections were made to each strand in each beam, denoted AS1 and AS2 for beam A to ES1 and ES2 for beam E. These three wires were run to a junction box near the ground on Pier 3, Figure 35. For simplicity all reinforcement measurements were connected together. Readings were taken from the box and directly from the beam end at time of installation to ensure that the additional cable run did not result in any change in readings.

3.4 Monitoring and Performance

Field impedance measurements of the EIT tendons were conducted at key stages in construction. The first measurement was prior to tensioning and after tensioning but prior to grouting. The purpose of these measurements are to first ensure that a short is not present between the tendon and the beam reinforcement. Assuming that a high AC resistance is measured, the post-tensioning measurement ensures that the ducts were not damaged during tensioning operations. The next measurement taken was immediately following grouting. At this point the resistance drops precipitously due to the encasement of the PT tendons in the wet grout. Measurements were taken regularly with the key measurements taken at 28 days after grout placement. Additional measurements were taken during placement of the beam diaphragms and deck. All measurements were taken with a BK Precision model 880 LCR meter with excitation voltage set at 0.6 V and test frequency of 1 kHz. The specific resistance measurements are summarized in Table 2 and illustrated in Figure 40. The specific capacitance and loss factor measurements are illustrated in Figure 41 and Figure 42. It is important to note that the standard, non-EIT, tendons are not isolated from the beam reinforcement. Impedance checks of the standard PT tendons after grouting indicated electrical continuity as expected and no further monitoring was conducted.

3.4.1 Acceptance Criteria

Acceptable performance of the system is assessed at various stages. After stressing the AC resistance of the strands should be greater than 10 Ohms (Fuzier, Ganz, and Matt 2005). Values less than this are indicative of direct contact between the tendon strands and beam steel. At this stage the capacitance and loss factor are not measured since grout

is not present. At an age of 28 days after grouting the Coplay bridge required a specific resistance greater than 50 kOhm-m. This value is in accordance with U.S. draft guidelines (Angst and Buchler 2015) which also permit up to a 10% failure rate for bridges where basic monitoring is conducted. For special situations where fatigue loading controls or stray current is present, higher requirements are prescribed. The fib bulletin 33 (Fuzier, Ganz, and Matt 2005) prescribes acceptable performance based on the duct diameter. Laboratory testing was conducted on a specific duct known as PT-Plus which is different than what was used in the Coplay Bridge. For 76 mm PT-Plus ducts the specific resistance should be greater than 400kOhm-m, less than 3.05 nF/m, and have a loss factor less than 0.1. The specific resistance and capacitance change to 300 kOhm-m and 3.35 nF/m for 100 mm ducts. These values have been removed from recent recommendations including the U.S. draft standard since thresholds vary based on duct material and wall thickness. Additional research is needed to develop these values for each commercially available system before limits can be prescribed.

Tendon Lengths [m]:		166.83	166.00	165.31	164.62	163.92
Beam ID		AE	BE	CE	DE	EE
Age of Grout [days]	Temperature [C]	[kOhm-m]	[kOhm-m]	[kOhm-m]	[kOhm-m]	[kOhm-m]
Prior to Tension	4.4	26693	13280	9877	19754	11474
Post-Tension	N.A.	28695	11786	7325	27409	18588
0	N.A.	35	41	20	10	23
1	10.0	53	61	33	42	32
3	1.7	81	92	49	77	58
7	5.0	92	104	55	96	65
9	15.6	98	112	56	108	72
14	10.0	141	154	83	149	N.A.
16	7.2	171	172	90	178	119
17	3.3	211	196	106	212	144
28	5.6	254	246	137	223	168
42	3.3	296	298	156	257	203
86	-5.6	656	581	370	451	484
167	15.6	450	388	219	279	264
185	13.3	535	457	253	340	327
352	22.2	1081	947	600	628	657

The EIT tendons in each of the five beams performed in accordance with the design specification requirements. High resistance values were observed both prior and following post-tensioning operations. This indicated that the beams did not have any major shorts prior to grouting. The tendons all achieved the 50 kOhm-m specific resistance requirement 7-days after grouting. By the required age of 28 days the specific resistances ranged from 137 to 254 kOhm-m. While the fib bulletin 33 requirements were not required for the bridge a comparison shows that: (1) the tendons exceeded the specific resistance of 300 kOhm-m at an age of 86 days, (2) the specific capacitance was less than the control value of 3.05 nF/m at all ages, and (3) the loss factor approached a value of 0.10 as the concrete and grout cured but only dropped below that value in beam A and B at an age of 86 days, and in all beams at an age of 352 days. Recall that the validity of the fib 33 requirements were not established for the duct used in the Coplay project. Beam line D which had marginal pressure loss due to cross-communication between the ducts resulted with the lowest initial specific resistance and highest specific capacitance readings as noted in Table 2. The resistance

improved rapidly as the grout cured leaving beam line C with the lowest resistance. As illustrated in Figures 7, 8 and 9, the specific resistance measurements appear to provide the most sensitivity to variations in encapsulation.

In general, the readings followed expected trends during the Fall construction season. The specific resistance increased, the capacitance and loss factors decreased. Construction was put on hold for the Winter and once the temperature reached reasonable levels, concrete placement restarted. The first Spring measurement was taken at a grout age of 167 days. This reading was taken within a week of placement of the east end diaphragm at Pier 6. At this stage a measurable decrease in resistance and increases in capacitance and loss factor were noted. It is expected that the presence of freshly placed concrete surrounding the east end of the tendon run resulted in the measured changes. Further measurements of the system taken at 185 days, a week after completion of the west end diaphragm at Pier 3, showed a reversal of the unexpected trend. The remaining construction consists of deck placement which due to the presence of epoxy coated bars was not expected to change the trend of the readings. Measurements at an age of 352 days indicates that the specific resistance values continued to increase as expected. Ambient temperature measurements were taken during each reading and are noted in Table 2. While a focused thermal study was not conducted, it does not appear that variations in temperature resulted in significant changes in measured impedance.

Figure 40: Specific resistance measurements of EIT system

Figure 41: Specific capacitance measurements of EIT system

Figure 42: Loss factor measurements of EIT system

3.5 Recommendations

Based on discussion with contractors and precast fabricators the EIT system did not require measurable increases in fabrication effort. Additional recommendations were suggested to improve quality assurance along the way. To help ensure the performance of the precast units a preliminary pressure check of the beams at the plant would be beneficial to ensure that they are sound before transportation and erection. This check could include a low pressure check prior to concrete placement at the plant and following initial curing. The closure joint spacing of 305 mm (12 in.) made splicing of the plastic ducts very difficult in the field. An increase in this distance would ease installation of couplers and proper attachment of heat shrink tubing, as an alternative, an improved coupling system would be advantageous.

To further understand the implications of the measurements taken additional research is needed. This should include characterization of acceptable specific capacitance and loss factors for the variety of ducts commercially available. These tests should also examine the impact of coupling techniques on the measured performance. Sensitivity tests should be completed to illustrate the impact of defect size and chloride intrusion on measurable changes in the specific resistance. The impact of grout type and inherent chloride content should also be examined.

3.6 Discussion and Conclusions

An electrically isolated tendon (EIT) system was demonstrated in the Coplay Bridge replacement project. The bridge system is composed of precast pretensioned Pennsylvania bulb tee beams that are field spliced and post-tensioned. This is the first application of EIT technology in the United States. An overview of the system was discussed along with detailing and measurement requirements.

The EIT system appears to provide a viable system for initial and long-term monitoring of encapsulation of the PT tendon. Installation of the EIT system was not significantly different than that of a conventional post-tensioning tendon and did not require any noticeable labor increase during precast or field operations. The system provided additional assurance of the electrical isolation in the bridge and appears to be a viable approach for long term monitoring of the performance of the tendons. Additional research is recommended to allow for better understanding of the performance of the system during long term monitoring and for establishment of a more comprehensive acceptance criteria.

4 EIT MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

Additional details are provided on the EIT measurement boxes and installation in this chapter.

4.1 EIT Monitoring System

In order to conduct the electrical impedance measurements, a junction box was installed on pier 3, with wires running up to connect to the EIT strands and the reinforcement outside of the ducts. The location of the junction box can be seen below in Figure 43. Figure 44 shows how the wires are connected to the prestressing strands running through each beam. The beam ends were cast into the end diaphragm of the bridge. To protect the wire ends the wires were put in conduit prior to diaphragm concrete placement. The details are shown in Figure 44 and Figure 45. To take the measurements, a handheld LCR meter is hooked up to the box, and the resistance, capacitance, and loss factor values can be read off the meter. Figure 46 displays a close-up view of the box with the LCR meter attached.

Figure 43: EIT junction box location

Figure 44: EIT and strand wire housing in diaphragm

Figure 45: Conduit connection to strands

Figure 46: EIT box close-up

4.2 EIT Box Details

The connectivity for installation of the EIT box is illustrated in Figure 47. Note that due to construction stages the reinforcement cage was not present during installation of the box. Consequently, the reinforcement cage wires, R1 and R2 cage were not used in the box. The beam steel from the continuity prestressing strand was adequate to complete the LCR circuit and perform all measurements.

The hardware purchased for the box installation is summarized in Table 3. It is important to note that measurements taken 6 months after installation indicated moisture accumulation in the box. The source was likely due to condensation on the vertical pipe. For future installations it is recommended that a drainage vent be installed before the conduit enters the EIT box. The conduit should also be sealed prior to entry into the EIT box. Putty was post-installed in the box to reduce water accumulation.

Figure 47: Wiring diagram for EIT Box

Table 3: EIT Box Hardware	
	<p>Washdown Enclosure with – Powder Coated Steel with Side Hinge and Slotted Latch</p> <p>Description: These enclosures are rated NEMA 4 for protection from dirt and washdowns. NEMA 12 rated enclosures also protect from oil/coolant dripping.</p> <p>Enclosures with a slotted latch open with a quarter turn for easy access—there are no clamps or screws to unfasten.</p> <p>Detail: Height 16 in. x width 16 in x Depth 6 in. Mounting consists of 4 – ½ in. diameter holes. Concealed hinge and Gasketed cover. Gray</p> <p>Quantity: 1</p> <p>McMaster-Carr Part: 7812K23</p>

Table 3: EIT Box Hardware

	<p><u>Terminal Blocks – 600V AC / 600V DC – 90A per Circuit</u></p> <p>Description: 1.125 in. Terminal Center to Center. UK Recognized, CSA Certified, CE Marked</p> <p>Detail: For 3 Circuit, for wire 8-2 Screw terminals, ¼ in. size, Length 5.125in., Width 2.5 in, Height 1.125 in.</p> <p>Quantity: 5</p> <p>McMaster-Carr Part: 5566T72</p>
	<p><u>Underground Heat-Shrink Screw-Down Butt Splice</u></p> <p>Description: For watertight connections for underground applications. These splices are abrasion-resistant and can withstand burial in rocky soil. They come with a length of heavy-wall polyolefin heat-shrink tubing that fits over the splice. Tighten the screws to connect wires.</p> <p>Detail: Single Wire splice with 2 and 5 in. of heat shrink tubing. Shrink temp 250F Max temp 190F. Terminal tinplated aluminum. Insulation Polyolefin Plastic. For copper or aluminum wire gauge 8-2.</p> <p>Quantity: 15</p> <p>McMaster-Carr Part: 7924K12</p>
	<p><u>Set Screw Lugs</u></p> <p>Description: The straight tongue improves conductivity by increasing the surface contact between the lug and your equipment. Tighten the set screw onto your wire for a secure connection without crimping. Mount lugs to a screw.</p> <p>Detail: For Wire gauge 14-4. Single Wire. Screw Size 0.25 in., Lg 1.060, Wd 0.50, Ht 0.50, aluminum for 600V.</p> <p>Quantity: 15</p> <p>McMaster-Carr Part: 6920K21</p>
<p>Single Nut</p>	<p><u>Grounding Rod Clamps</u></p> <p>Description: Connect bare-copper ground wire to grounding rods. These clamps meet UL 467 for direct burial.</p> <p>Detail: For ½” diameter rod, For wire gauge size 10-2, Copper alloy.</p> <p>Quantity: 10</p> <p>McMaster-Carr Part:7491K73</p>
	<p><u>Building Cable for Wet Locations</u></p> <p>Description: Bend and Stay, Temperature Range: 10° to 190° F, Insulation: Inner and outer is PVC, Often used as outdoor feeder cable for pumps and lighting, this cable is also known as type UF-B. It can be used for direct burial without conduit. The insulation resists moisture and UV light. There is an uninsulated</p>

Table 3: EIT Box Hardware

	<p>ground wire that is not counted in the number of wires. To connect to enclosures or outlet boxes, use cord grips for building cable (not included).</p> <p>Detail: 12 Gauge, 3 Wire, 20A, 600VAC, Insulation color black, red, white, outer insulation gray.</p> <p>Quantity: Two 250ft</p> <p>McMaster-Carr Part: 7116K96</p>
--	---

4.3 LCR Meter Requirements

All measurements should be conducted with an LCR meter. The meter used for the research effort consists of a BK Precision 880 LCR Meter. The specifications of the meter are shown in Figure 48. A CMT-437 LCR meter available in Europe was used by DSI International as part of this study. In accordance with the SGK requirements (Angst and Buchler 2015), the LCR Meter must have the following capabilities to be viable for EIT measurements.

- Measuring voltage amplitude: minimum 0.5 V alternating voltage
- Measuring frequency: 1 kHz
- Circuit Setting: Set circuit to PARALLEL (not Series)
- Measuring range:
 - Ohmic resistance, R: 0.1 to 10M Ω (with a resolution of 0.1 Ω at the lower end of the range.
 - Capacitance, C: 0.1 nF to 100 μ F
 - Loss factor, D: 0.001 to 10

Data Sheet

40,000-Count Dual-Display Handheld LCR Meters Models 878B, 879B, and 880

Full Featured Handheld LCR Meters

The 878B, 879B, and 880 40,000-count handheld LCR meters measure inductance, capacitance, and resistance quickly and precisely. The 879B and 880 also measure impedance, Theta, and ESR. Additionally, the 880 offers capabilities typically only found in bench LCR meters such as a 4-terminal configuration, basic measurement accuracy up to 0.1% test frequencies up to 100 kHz, selectable test signal levels and measurement rate.

Fast auto ranging and quick measurement configuration such as measurement parameter and test frequency selection make these meters very simple to operate. The meters also include handy functions such as data hold, Min/Max/Average recording, tolerance sorting, and relative mode.

Measurement data can continuously transfer to a PC via the meter's mini USB interface, using either the provided data logging software or SCPI commands sent from a custom program.

ESR Measurements

Models 879B and 880 have the ability to measure the ESR (Equivalent Series Resistance) of capacitors. ESR is the sum of in-phase AC resistance of a capacitor and used to rate a capacitor's quality. An ideal capacitor would be lossless and have an ESR of zero. A capacitor could measure the correct capacitance value, yet still be defective, due to the component's excessive in-phase AC resistance. The 879B and 880 would be able to detect this faulty component.

Features & Benefits

- 40,000 counts resolution on primary and 10,000 counts resolution on secondary display
- L, C, R and Z (879B & 880 only) primary measurements
- Automatic calculation of secondary parameters D, Q, θ , ESR (θ /ESR for 879B & 880 only), DCR (880 only)
- Accuracy up to 0.1% and selectable test frequencies up to 100 kHz (880 only)
- Fast auto range design for rapid, easy component measurements
- Auto detect mode for automatic component type identification and measurement type selection (880 only)
- Relative mode
- Visible and audible tolerance mode
- Data Hold and Min/Max/Average recording
- USB (Virtual COM) interface
- SCPI compliant commands for remote communication
- Software for datalogging and front panel emulation available as free download
- Configurable power-up-states
- 3 year warranty

Applications

- Passive component troubleshooting
- Electronic assembly
- Quality control (component sorting)

Specifications	878B	879B	880
Measurements	L, C, R, D, Q	L, C, R, Z, D, Q, θ , ESR	L, C, R, Z, D, Q, θ , ESR & DCR
Basic Accuracy	0.5%	0.5%	0.1%
Test Frequency	120 Hz, 1 kHz	100 Hz, 120 Hz, 1 kHz, 10 kHz	100 Hz, 120 Hz, 1 kHz, 10 kHz, 100 kHz
Test Signal	0.6 Vrms	0.6 Vrms	0.3 Vrms, 0.6 Vrms, 1 Vrms DCR: 1 Vdc
Backlit Display	-	✓	✓
Auto Detect Mode	-	-	✓
Tolerance Mode	1%, 5%, 10%	1%, 5%, 10%, 20%	1%, 5%, 10%, 20%
Measurement Rate	1.5 readings/sec	1.5 readings/sec	4 readings/sec (fast), 1.5 readings/sec (slow)

Technical data subject to change
© B&K Precision Corp. 2016

www.bkprecision.com

Figure 48: BK LCR Meter Specification Sheet

4.4 Sample EIT Measurement Record

A sample EIT measurement record sheet is provided. The sheet is developed to allow for long term tracking of the performance of the system and includes supplemental data to help interpret the performance. A sample filled in form using the Coplay Bridge Project data is shown in Figure 49. A blank sheet is shown in Figure 50.

EIT Measurement Record

Bridge Identification: Copley Bridge S.R. 7404

Ensure LCR Meter Settings!!!
 AC Resistance Circuit: PAL (Parallel) Frequency: 1.0 kHz Excitation: 0.6V

Tendon Grouted:	10/23/18	Tendon ID:	AE	BE	CE	DE	EE
		Tendon Location:	Beam 16	Beam 17	Beam 18	Beam 19	Beam 20
		Tendon Lengths [ft]:	547.34	544.63	542.36	540.08	537.79
		Tendon Lengths [m]:	166.83	166.00	165.31	164.62	163.92

#	Date of Reading	Time	Age [days]	Operator [Initials]	Temp. [F]	Beam AE			Beam BE		
						R [Ohms]	C [nF]	D	R [Ohms]	C [nF]	D
A	10/22/18	8:45 AM	Pretension	CJN	40	160,000	NA	NA	80,000	NA	NA
B	10/22/18	10:00 AM	Post-Ten	DSI	unk.	172,000	NA	NA	71,000	NA	NA
C	10/23/18	unk	0	DSI	unk.	212	-	-	247	-	-
D	10/24/18	1:30 PM	1	MJG	50	319	-	-	370	-	-
E	10/26/18	8:30 AM	3	MB	35	484.3	-	-	555.9	-	-
F	10/30/18	8:30 AM	7	MB	41	551.1	490.0	0.671	625.9	481.1	0.595
G	11/1/18	8:30 AM	9	MB	60	589.9	483.2	0.597	673.4	478.9	0.531
H	11/6/18	8:30 AM	14	MB	50	846.4	484.3	0.557	924.7	479.4	0.493
I	11/8/2018	8:30 AM	16	MB	45	1026.6	474.4	0.395	1033.9	472.3	0.364
J	11/9/18	9:25 AM	17	CJN	38	1264.0	474.7	0.327	1180.0	475.9	0.323
K	11/20/18	8:40 AM	28	CJN	42	1521.6	471.9	0.267	1483.4	473.3	0.284
L	12/4/18	9:00 AM	42	MB	38	1774.7	472.2	0.222	1792.2	472.3	0.227
M	1/17/2019	8:30 AM	86	MB	22	3932.1	471.2	0.190	3501.2	471.2	0.189
N	4/8/2019	8:30 AM	167	MB	60	2695.0	462.2	0.088	2334.4	461.9	0.098
O	4/26/2019	12:00 PM	185	CJN	56	3209.7	471.2	0.125	2750.9	470.7	0.145
P	10/10/2019	1:27 PM	352	CJN	72	6480.0	469.7	0.106	5706.0	469.4	0.123

EIT Measurement Record

Bridge Identification: Copley Bridge S.R. 7404

Ensure LCR Meter Settings!!!
 AC Resistance Circuit: PAL (Parallel) Frequency: 1.0 kHz Excitation: 0.6V

Tendon Grouted:	10/23/18	Tendon ID:	AE	BE	CE	DE	EE
		Tendon Location:	Beam 16	Beam 17	Beam 18	Beam 19	Beam 20
		Tendon Lengths [ft]:	547.34	544.63	542.36	540.08	537.79
		Tendon Lengths [m]:	166.83	166.00	165.31	164.62	163.92

#	Date of Reading	Beam CE			Beam DE			Beam EE			Comments:
		R [Ohms]	C [nF]	D	R [Ohms]	C [nF]	D	R [Ohms]	C [nF]	D	
A	10/22/18	60,000	NA	NA	120,000	NA	NA	70,000	NA	NA	
B	10/22/18	44,500	NA	NA	166,500	NA	NA	113,400	NA	NA	
C	10/23/18	120	-	-	58.0	-	-	139.0	-	-	
D	10/24/18	202	-	-	257.8	-	-	196.5	-	-	
E	10/26/18	300.2	-	-	465.8	-	-	355.9	-	-	
F	10/30/18	337.1	482.5	1.093	585.3	494.9	0.690	394.1	480.1	0.931	
G	11/1/18	342.0	481.8	0.981	655.8	482.6	0.565	440.5	475.9	0.848	
H	11/6/18	503.5	483.2	0.963	906.4	483.0	0.502	NA	474.2	0.761	
I	11/8/2018	546.1	474.4	0.666	1,080.7	472.8	0.371	723.3	NA	NA	
J	11/9/18	641.3	478.8	0.609	1,286.0	473.9	0.311	871.8	466.4	0.472	
K	11/20/18	830.2	473.4	0.523	1,351.8	470.5	0.263	1,021.2	463.0	0.394	
L	12/4/18	947.1	472.5	0.406	1,562.5	471.1	0.250	1,235.3	463.7	0.336	
M	1/17/2019	2245.1	473.0	0.356	2,738.1	470.1	0.217	2,940.0	463.6	0.278	
N	4/8/2019	1328.2	460.2	0.154	1,697.5	460.2	0.126	1,600.8	454.4	0.119	
O	4/26/2019	1539.2	474.2	0.253	2,063.0	473.4	0.198	1,985.4	466.2	0.213	
P	10/10/2019	3642.0	471.7	0.219	3,816.0	472.2	0.163	3,991.0	465.2	0.172	

Figure 49: Copley recorded raw data

EIT Measurement Record

Page

Bridge Identification:

Ensure LCR Meter Settings!!!			
AC Resistance	Circuit: PAL (Parallel)	Frequency: 1.0 kHz	Excitation: 0.6V

Tendon Grouted:		Tendon ID:					
		Tendon Location:					
		Tendon Lengths [ft]:					
		Tendon Lengths [m]:					

#	Date of Reading	Time	Age [days]	Operator [Initials]	Temp. [F]				Comments
						R [Ohms]	C [nF]	D	
A			Pretension						
B			Post-Ten						
C									
D									
E									
F									
G									
H									
I									
J									
K									
L									
M									
N									
O									
P									

Figure 50: Sample blank data sheet

5 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to acknowledge that the EIT demonstration was supported through funding from the Federal Highway Administration Project DTFH61-11-H-0027 Advancing Steel and Concrete Bridge Technology to Improve Infrastructure Performance. The oversight provided by the author and installation of the monitoring box was funded by the Pennsylvania Department of Transportation. The author would like to thank the people involved in the fabrication, erection and construction of the bridge for their interaction and support during the project. Specifically, Reggie Holt of FHWA, Tom Macioce and Timothy Carre of PennDOT, Larry Franko of Pennoni, Troy Jenkins of Northeast Prestressed Products, Jared Musser of Trumbull, Joe Salvadori and Shahid Islam of DSI, and William Nickas of the Prestressed/Precast Institute. Special thanks to graduate student Maximillian Beedle who tirelessly assisted with field measurements in harsh weather conditions and student Helen Whalen who assisted with some of the initial site visits.

REFERENCES

- AASHTO. 2017. "AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Specifications, 8th Edition." Washington, DC.
- Angst, Ueli, and Markus Buchler. 2015. "Monitorable Post-Tensioning Systems Sub Task 2 - State of the Art Report." SGK Swiss Society for Corrosion Protection.
- ASTM International. 2017. *ASTM A416-17 Standard Specification for Low-Relaxation, Seven-Wire Steel Strand for Prestressed Concrete*. <https://doi.org/10.1520/A0416>.
- ASTM Standard C942-15. 2015. "Standard Test Method for Compressive Strength of Grouts for Preplaced-Aggregate Concrete in the Laboratory." West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International. <https://doi.org/10.1520/C0942-15>.
- ASTM Standard C953-17. 2017. "Standard Test Method for Time of Setting of Grouts for Preplaced-Aggregate Concrete in the Laboratory." West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International. <https://doi.org/10.1520/C0953-17>.
- ASTM Standard C1202-19. 2019. "Standard Test Method for Electrical Indication of Concretes Ability to Resist Chloride Ion Penetration." West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International. <https://doi.org/10.1520/C1202-19>.
- ASTM Standard D4101-17. 2017. "Standard Classification System and Basis for Specification for Polypropylene Injection and Extrusion Materials." West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International. <https://doi.org/10.1520/D4101-17>.
- Berg, Kyle Matthew, and Andrea J Schokker. 2012. "Development of Best Practices for Inspection of PT Bridges in Minnesota," 213.
- Corven Engineering, Inc. 2001. "Mid-Bay Bridge Post-Tensioning Evaluation." https://fdotwww.blob.core.windows.net/sitefinity/docs/default-source/content/structures/posttensioning/mid-bay-final-report-w-append.pdf?sfvrsn=fd956447_0.
- Elsener, B. 2005. "Long-Term Monitoring of Electrically Isolated Post-Tensioning Tendons." *Structural Concrete* 6 (3): 101–6. <https://doi.org/10.1680/stco.2005.6.3.101>.
- Elsener, Bernhard. 2004. "Electrical Isolation as Enhanced Protection for Posttensioning Tendons in Concrete Structures (PL 3)." In *Proceedings of the First Workshop of COST 534 on NDT Assessment and New Systems in Prestressed Concrete Structures*, 73–79.
- . 2008. "Monitoring of Electrically Isolated Post-Tensioning Tendons." In *Tailor Made Concrete Structures*, edited by Joost Walraven and Dick Stoelhorst. CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781439828410>.
- Elsener, Bernhard, and Markus Büchler. 2011. "Quality Control and Monitoring of Electrically Isolated Post-Tensioning Tendons in Bridges." ETH Zurich. <https://doi.org/10.3929/ethz-a-006883522>.
- Fuzier, Jean-Philippe, Hans-Rudolf Ganz, and Peter Matt. 2005. *Durability of Post-Tensioning Tendons FIB33*. Bulletin / International Federation for Structural Concrete Recommendation 33. Lausanne: fib.
- Goldsberry, Ben. 2013. "Post-Tensioning Best Practice Update and New Directions for PostTensioned Structures." presented at the 2013 Design Training Expo, Florida Department of Transportation.
- Hartt, William, and SK Lee. 2018. "Corrosion Forecasting and Failure Projection of Post-Tension Tendons in Deficient Cementitious Grout." FHWA-HRT-17-074. <https://www.fhwa.dot.gov/publications/research/infrastructure/bridge/17074/17074.pdf>.
- Mathy, B, P Demars, F Roisin, and M Wouters. 1996. "Investigation and Strengthening Study of Twenty Damaged Bridges: A Belgium Case History." In *Bridge Management: Proceedings of the Third International Conference*, 658–66.
- Naito, Clay. 2020. "Construction and Field Evaluation of Electrically Isolated Tendons in a Prestressed Concrete Spliced Girder Bridge." *Journal of Bridge Engineering* 25 (7): 05020001. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)BE.1943-5592.0001551](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)BE.1943-5592.0001551).
- Post-Tensioning Institute (PTI) and American Segmental Bridge Institute (ASBI). 2012. "PTI/ASBI M50.3-12: Guide Specification for Grouted Post-Tensioning." PTI/ASBI M50.3-12.
- Powers, Rodney G, Alberto A Sagüés, and Yash Paul Virmani. n.d. "Corrosion of Post-Tensioned Tendons in Florida Bridges," 17.
- Suarez, Jorge, Jingyu Zhang, Grace Hsuan, and William Hartt. 2006. "Polyethylene Duct Cracking on Posttensioning Tendons in Florida Segmented Bridges." *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering* 18 (4): 581–87. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)0899-1561\(2006\)18:4\(581\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)0899-1561(2006)18:4(581)).
- Trejo, David, Mary Beth Hueste, Paolo Gardoni, Radhakrishna Pillai, Kenneth Reinschmidt, Seok Been Im, and Suresh Katrina. 2009. "Effect of Voids in Grouted, Post-Tensioned Concrete Bridge Construction: Volume

- 1 – Electrochemical Testing and Reliability Assessment.” FHWA/TX-09/0-4588-1 Vol. 1. Texas Transportation Institute.
- Vedova, Della, and Bernhard Elsener. 2006. “Enhanced Durability, Quality Control and Monitoring of Electrically Isolated Tendons.” In , 13. Naples, Italy.
- Vedova, M Della, B Elsener, and L Evangelista. 2004. “Corrosion Protection and Monitoring of Electrically Isolated Post-Tensioning Tendons.” In *Proceedings of the Third European Conference on Structural Control*, 5. Vienna, Austria.
- Woodward, R J. 1981. “Conditions Within Ducts in Post-Tensioned Prestressed Concrete Bridges.” TRRL 980. Transport and Road Research Laboratory: Bridges Division Structures Department Transport and Road Research Laboratory Crowthorne, Berkshire.

APPENDIX A: SITE VISIT SUMMARY

A series of site visits were conducted during the project. Summary slides were developed following each visit and are attached here as an appendix.

Federal Highway Administration Project DTFH61-11-H-0027
Advancing Steel and Concrete Bridge Technology to Improve Infrastructure Performance
Task No. 14

Construction and Field Evaluation of Electrically Isolated Tendons in a Precast/Prestressed/Post-Tensioned Concrete Spliced Girder Bridge

Coplay Bridge (S.R. 704)

Clay Naito, Ph.D., P.E.
July 23, 2018
Field Notes

LEHIGH
UNIVERSITY

Overview

- ▶ Owner - Lehigh / Northampton County
- ▶ Construction Oversight Project Management - Pennoni
- ▶ Designer - AECOM
- ▶ Bridge Beam Producer - Northeast Prestressed Products, Cressona PA
- ▶ Post-Tension Contractor - DSI
- ▶ Bridge Construction - Trumbull Corporation
- ▶ Bridge Beam Erector - Structural Services

Site Visit 02-12-2018

- ▶ NPP Onsite - Troy Jenkins & C. Naito
- ▶ Installation Demonstration of grout connections

Site Visit 02-12-2018

- ▶ NPP Onsite - Troy Jenkins & C. Naito
- ▶ Early layout of PT ducts

Top duct is EIT

Duct protection at stirrups

Site Visit 02-23-2018

- ▶ NPP Onsite - Troy Jenkins & C. Naito
- ▶ Completed beams and End Anchorage Fabrication

EIT Duct and
Isolated
Anchorage Head

Lip

Non-Isolated
Anchorage Head
and Duct

Site Visit 02-23-2018

- ▶ NPP Onsite - Troy Jenkins & C. Naito
- ▶ Completed beams and End Anchorage Fabrication

Site Visit 03-14-2018

- ▶ NPP Onsite - Troy Jenkins & C. Naito
- ▶ Reinforcement Installation

Site Visit 03-14-2018

- ▶ NPP Onsite - Troy Jenkins & C. Naito
- ▶ Reinforcement Installation

Site Visit 07-13-2018

- ▶ Onsite - Larry Franko (Pennoni), C. Naito & M. Gombeda (Lehigh)
- ▶ Location Coplay and Northampton Sides of Construction

Pier 1

Note if junction box is to be added it would go on either Pier 3 or 6.

Site Visit 07-13-2018

- ▶ Onsite - Larry Franko (Pennoni), C. Naito & M. Gombeda (Lehigh)
- ▶ Location Coplay and Northampton Sides of Construction
- ▶ Notes
 - ▶ Beams to arrive on site on July 20.
 - ▶ Five Haunch beams to erected first with two on site and two down the road. Fifth to arrive on Monday 7/23
 - ▶ Erection to start on 7/23
 - ▶ Splice beams for span 6 (between Pier 5-6) to arrive next.
 - ▶ Same sequence to follow on Coplay side. Span 5 drop in beams to be placed last followed by Tensioning.
 - ▶ Estimated PT Installation (AFTER September 3)

Site Visit 07-23-2018

- ▶ Onsite - Larry Franko (Pennoni), C. Naito & M. Gombeda (Lehigh)
- ▶ Location Northampton Side of Construction
- ▶ Erection of Span 6 Beams

APPENDIX B: FIELD INSPECTION REQUIREMENTS

An abbreviated inspection requirement is included for future field inspection of the Coplay Bridge. The summary recommendation is included in this Appendix.

EIT INSPECTION GUIDELINE FOR COPLAY (S.R. 704) BRIDGE

This brief report provides guidance on how to take measurements of the EIT system installed at the Coplay State Route 704 Bridge. Any questions regarding the readings can be directed to Professor Clay Naito (cjn3@lehigh.edu). Further details on the system and installation can be found in ATLSS Report 20-03.

Naito, C., "Construction and Field Evaluation of Electrically Isolated Tendons in a Precast/Prestressed/Post-Tensioned Concrete Spliced Girder Bridge - Coplay Bridge (S.R. 704)," ATLSS Report No. 20-03, ATLSS Center, Lehigh University, April 2020.

1.1 Box Location

The EIT box is located at Pier 3 on the Coplay side of the bridge (Figure 1). The box is located at a height of approximately 10 ft off the ground (to limit vandalism) and requires a ladder for access see Figure 2a. The box is NOT LOCKED, simply use a coin or screwdriver to open the door see Figure 2b.

Figure 1: EIT Box Location

Figure 2: EIT Measurement

1.2 Measurement Device

All measurements should be conducted with an LCR meter. The LCR meter must have the following capabilities to be viable for EIT measurements as noted below. A BK Precision 880 LCR Meter (available on Amazon in 2020) was used for the initial study see Figure 2c. Other viable LCR meters include the CMT-437 LCR meter or the Keysight Technologies U1733C meter.

Measuring voltage amplitude: minimum 0.5 V alternating voltage

Measuring frequency: 1 kHz

Circuit Setting:	Set circuit to PARALLEL (not Series)
Measuring range:	Ohmic resistance, R: 0.1 to 10M Ω (with a resolution of 0.1 Ω at the lower end of the range. Capacitance, C: 0.1 nF to 100 μ F Loss factor, D: 0.001 to 10

1.3 Measurements

To take readings follow the steps below:

- Configure LCR Meter
 - Set device to Parallel circuit reading
 - Set Excitation Voltage to at least 0.5 Volts (Note that the BK 880 was set to 0.6V)
 - Set Excitation Frequency to 1 kHz
 - Read the manual so you know how to measure Resistance, R, Capacitance, C, and loss factor, D.
- Note Conditions: Local temperature, Time of measurement, Name of person taking measurement
- Open Box on Bridge
- Connect one meter lead to the “Beam Steel” measurement stud.
- Connect secondary meter lead to the measurement stud locations one at a time: AE, BE, CE, DE, EE
- For each connection AE through EE, measure R (in Ohms, Ω), C (in nano-farads, nF), and D (no units) from meter (this may require operator to toggle through LCR meter to change measurement from Resistance to Capacitance to Loss Factor).
- Record results on attached sheets.
- REVIEW readings before leaving.
 - Resistance should continue to increase with age (alert PennDOT if a reading is LESS THAN the previous reading)
 - Capacitance and Loss factor should decrease with age (alert PennDOT if reading is GREATER THAN previous reading)
 - IF ALL readings are considerably different than previous readings it is highly likely that measurement was done incorrectly. Check LCR meter settings and connection and redo measurements.

EIT Measurement Record

Bridge Identification: Coplay Bridge S.R. 7404

Ensure LCR Meter Settings!!!

AC Resistance Circuit: PAL (Parallel) Frequency: 1.0 kHz Excitation: 0.6V

Tendon
Grouted
10/23/18

Tendon ID:	AE	BE	CE	DE	EE
Tendon Location:	Beam 16	Beam 17	Beam 18	Beam 19	Beam 20
Tendon Lengths [ft]:	547.34	544.63	542.36	540.08	537.79
Tendon Lengths [m]:	166.83	166.00	165.31	164.62	163.92

#	Date of Reading	Time	Age [days]	Operator [Initials]	Temp. [F]	Beam AE			Beam BE		
						R [Ohms]	C [nF]	D	R [Ohms]	C [nF]	D
A	10/22/18	8:45 AM	Pretension	CJN	40	160,000	NA	NA	80,000	NA	NA
B	10/22/18	10:00 AM	Post-Ten	DSI	unk.	172,000	NA	NA	71,000	NA	NA
C	10/23/18	unk	0	DSI	unk.	212	-	-	247	-	-
D	10/24/18	1:30 PM	1	MJG	50	319	-	-	370	-	-
E	10/26/18	8:30 AM	3	MB	35	484.3	-	-	555.9	-	-
F	10/30/18	8:30 AM	7	MB	41	551.1	490.0	0.671	625.9	481.1	0.595
G	11/1/18	8:30 AM	9	MB	60	589.9	483.2	0.597	673.4	478.9	0.531
H	11/6/18	8:30 AM	14	MB	50	846.4	484.3	0.557	924.7	479.4	0.493
I	11/8/2018	8:30 AM	16	MB	45	1026.6	474.4	0.395	1033.9	472.3	0.364
J	11/9/18	9:25 AM	17	CJN	38	1264.0	474.7	0.327	1180.0	475.9	0.323
K	11/20/18	8:40 AM	28	CJN	42	1521.6	471.9	0.267	1483.4	473.3	0.284
L	12/4/18	9:00 AM	42	MB	38	1774.7	472.2	0.222	1792.2	472.3	0.227
M	1/17/2019	8:30 AM	86	MB	22	3932.1	471.2	0.190	3501.2	471.2	0.189
N	4/8/2019	8:30 AM	167	MB	60	2695.0	462.2	0.088	2334.4	461.9	0.098
O	4/26/2019	12:00 PM	185	CJN	56	3209.7	471.2	0.125	2750.9	470.7	0.145
P	10/10/2019	1:27 PM	352	CJN	72	6480.0	469.7	0.106	5706.0	469.4	0.123
Q											
R											
S											
T											
U											
V											
W											
X											
Y											
Z											

EIT Measurement Record

Bridge Identification: Coplay Bridge S.R. 7404

Ensure LCR Meter Settings!!!

AC Resistance Circuit: PAL (Parallel) Frequency: 1.0 kHz Excitation: 0.6V

Tendon
Grouted
10/23/18

Tendon ID:	AE	BE	CE	DE	EE
Tendon Location:	Beam 16	Beam 17	Beam 18	Beam 19	Beam 20
Tendon Lengths [ft]:	547.34	544.63	542.36	540.08	537.79
Tendon Lengths [m]:	166.83	166.00	165.31	164.62	163.92

#	Date of Reading	Beam CE			Beam DE			Beam EE			Comments:
		R	C	D	R	C	D	R	C	D	
		[Ohms]	[nF]		[Ohms]	[nF]		[Ohms]	[nF]		
A	10/22/18	60,000	NA	NA	120,000	NA	NA	70,000	NA	NA	
B	10/22/18	44,500	NA	NA	166,500	NA	NA	113,400	NA	NA	
C	10/23/18	120	-	-	58.0	-	-	139.0	-	-	
D	10/24/18	202	-	-	257.8	-	-	196.5	-	-	
E	10/26/18	300.2	-	-	465.8	-	-	355.9	-	-	
F	10/30/18	337.1	482.5	1.093	585.3	494.9	0.690	394.1	480.1	0.931	
G	11/1/18	342.0	481.8	0.981	655.8	482.6	0.565	440.5	475.9	0.848	
H	11/6/18	503.5	483.2	0.963	906.4	483.0	0.502	NA	474.2	0.761	
I	11/8/2018	546.1	474.4	0.666	1,080.7	472.8	0.371	723.3	NA	NA	
J	11/9/18	641.3	478.8	0.609	1,286.0	473.9	0.311	871.8	466.4	0.472	
K	11/20/18	830.2	473.4	0.523	1,351.8	470.5	0.263	1,021.2	463.0	0.394	
L	12/4/18	947.1	472.5	0.406	1,562.5	471.1	0.250	1,235.3	463.7	0.336	
M	1/17/2019	2245.1	473.0	0.356	2,738.1	470.1	0.217	2,940.0	463.6	0.278	
N	4/8/2019	1328.2	460.2	0.154	1,697.5	460.2	0.126	1,600.8	454.4	0.119	
O	4/26/2019	1539.2	474.2	0.253	2,063.0	473.4	0.198	1,985.4	466.2	0.213	
P	10/10/2019	3642.0	471.7	0.219	3,816.0	472.2	0.163	3,991.0	465.2	0.172	
Q											
R											
S											
T											
U											
V											
W											
X											
Y											
Z											